

Applications for Directional Modulation on a Digital Phased Array

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Abstract—Whereas traditional beamforming concepts for phased arrays transmit the same signal content in all directions, shaped in magnitude by the array factor and element patterns, a phased array system employing directional modulation presented here forms a signal in a desired direction through spatial combination using a solution of randomized phase weights applied across the array. In a radar system application, these randomized phased weights are applied over many time segments of a radar pulse compression waveform. Matched filters trained on the spatially varying signal projected in a particular direction respond preferentially to the signals in these directions, while partial orthogonality with respect to the signal in other directions allows for directionally dependent responses to reflected returns from a target. Effective transmit patterns for these matched filter banks are shown. Additionally, coupling on the array as a function of scan angle and the randomized phase weights is characterized.

I. INTRODUCTION

With recent pushes into implementing full digital transceivers at every element in large phased array systems, applications requiring high levels of waveform agility and independently operating elements are now more realistically achievable. This includes applications such as multifunctional apertures with different tasks allocated and reallocated over time across sections of an array, or MIMO radar with independent waveforms on different elements or subarrays. One such array application that would benefit from the waveform agility of a digital phased array, termed directional modulation, has been demonstrated on smaller four-element arrays and shown to narrow the effective information beam by methodically distorting the array factor at every data symbol [1]. In previous implementations with directional modulation, the systems applied a set of phase shifts between elements such that the combined radiated signal forms a desired symbol sequence in a particular angular direction, while that sequence was distorted off that direction, as in Fig. 1. These distortions can be optimized such that the received bit error rate (BER) falls off faster with respect to angle than a standard array of the same physical configuration. This provides some physical layer security by increasing the BER on potential eavesdroppers [2].

These same concepts are easily applied to digital phased arrays and used in radar applications. Where previous implementations relied on hardware based phase shifters on each element, typical digital phased arrays implement phase

Fig. 1. While traditional beamforming transmits the same signal in all directions (top), directional modulation (bottom) in a phased array system generates a spatially varying waveform, which can be used for generating a signal in a particular direction and tailored distortions in other directions.

shifts at base band, either through a configuration setting in a direct digital synthesizer (DDS) or arbitrary waveform generator. The effective number phase shifter states in a digital beamforming network is much greater than for typical analog beamformers—e.g. 16 bits of phase shift control for digital arrays versus 6-8 bits for analog. The finer granularity of phase states allows for a wider set of viable phase weights that produce a desired symbol in a desired direction, creating greater spatial variation of the transmitted waveform, which exploited for angular localization of targets [3].

It was shown in [3] that a set of randomized and partially independent waveforms constructed for a two-by-two planar array could be used to generate an arbitrary radar pulse compression waveform in a desired direction. By precalculating the transmitted waveform sequences at offset angles from this desired direction, incorporating all effects from element locations and applied waveforms, matched filters can be created from these sequences. Then upon transmitting the element waveforms toward a target in space, the reflected return signal is passed through these matched filters and their relative output magnitudes of the matched filters provide indication of direction to the target.

These techniques will be expanded upon here to show how waveforms can be constructed for larger phased arrays. Effective patterns that result from tracking the matched filter peaks as a function of angle, as well as effects of the randomized phase weights on coupling are examined.

II. EFFECTIVE RADIATION PATTERNS

A. Waveform and matched filter generation

The signal incident at a target from a phased array—neglecting propagation loss—having N elements and using directional modulation is given by

$$y(t) = \mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)\mathbf{U}(t)s(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\theta, \phi)$ is the array manifold vector, $s(t)$ is an arbitrary signal and for radar applications would be pulse compression waveform, and $\mathbf{U}(t) = [e^{j\phi_1} \dots e^{j\phi_N}]$ is a vector of unitary phase weights that create the directional modulation effect. If the beam is steered toward the target, the array manifold becomes a vector of ones and the signal at the target reduces to

$$y(t) = s(t) \sum_{i=1}^N e^{j\phi_i}. \quad (2)$$

This summation can be set equal to a constant, P , creating two constraint equations for the phases and allowing for arbitrary selection of $N - 2$ of the weights within a prescribed set. With $P = N$, the array operates as a standard phased array and reducing P both increases the amount of distortion applied to $s(t)$ off the beam-steering angle and decreases the signal magnitude along the main beam direction.

Random selection of each the first $N - 2$ terms of ϕ_i within a simple bounded set is not a straightforward task, as there is an interdependence between the weights that enables a solution to the remaining weights. Subdividing the the array into smaller groups of elements and running the algorithm on these blocks simplifies the task and ensures randomization is evenly applied throughout the array scrambling weights. The P -value for each block consisting of M elements can be resized to $P' = MP/N$ such that the combination of all the elements is equivalent to P in the principal direction. A normalized constant $P_n = P/N$ is used from this point forward, where $P_n = 1$ is the case with no scrambling applied. For the work in this paper, scrambling weights were obtained using a greedy algorithm by splitting the arrays into the largest possible number of blocks consisting of four elements, such that the remaining elements could be solved in blocks of three. A directional modulation waveform for any array consisting of more than five elements can be divided in this manner.

Application of randomized phase weights on a phased array creates variations in the baseband content of a signal that vary over angle which can impart spatial information onto targets [3]. The time sequence at a particular angle from a phased array transmitting a directional modulation waveform can be precalculated with knowledge of the array geometry and proper calibration of the array. By strategically selecting

Fig. 2. Simulated transmitted signals sampled at these locations and used as matched filters.

a few training angles and determining the waveform in these directions, a series of matched filters can be created from these sequences. Passing the reflected return off a target through these matched filters generates peaks corresponding to the range of the target, while the relative magnitudes of these peaks convey information about the angular location of the target.

B. Measurement and simulation

A two-by-two array simulation in Matlab was created to demonstrate these concepts, based on the array properties of a panel attached to Purdue University’s digital array radar (DAR) test bed [4]. The horizontal element spacing was 47 mm and the vertical spacing was 46 mm. The carrier frequency used was 3.3 GHz and the baseband signal $s(t)$ used for (1) was a 13-bit Barker sequence, the actual pulse width of which was not important for the simulation, and was formed with one time sample per segment of the sequence. One set of scrambling weights was calculated with $P_n = 0.51$ for each chip of $s(t)$ and the weights randomly applied across the array. Matched filters were generated from the sampled sequences at the four angular directions indicated in Fig. 2, which aid in providing an indication that a target is offset in azimuth or elevation with respect to the primary scan direction.

After generating all the weight sequences for each element that include the beam steering weights, data symbols, and scrambling weight vectors, these sequences were applied to the DAR testbed in an anechoic chamber with a horn antenna acting as the target, as described further in [3]. The DAR was rotated to $\theta_{az} = 20^\circ$, $\theta_{az} = 0^\circ$, and $\theta_{az} = -20^\circ$ and the baseband sequences recorded at the horn antenna were passed through the bank of matched filters created earlier in the process. The outputs from the matched filters are shown in Fig. 3. As evident from these figures, the positive azimuth channel peak was higher than the negative azimuth channel peak when the target was in the negative azimuth direction, and vice versa.

The ratios of these peaks can indicate location of target if they are mapped out over angle. The sample angles at which the matched filters are generated from also have some

Fig. 3. Matched filter outputs over sample time index, using a 13-bit Barker sequence for $s(t)$ and $P = 2.1$ for targets located at (a) $\theta_{az} = +20^\circ$, (b) $\theta_{az} = 0^\circ$, (c) $\theta_{az} = -20^\circ$

importance. If the sample angles are close to the scanning direction, the matched filters will be too similar and the delta between azimuth channels or elevation channels will be too small. Conversely if the sample angles are too far away from the scanning direction, to the point where little energy is transmitted in that direction, outputs from the matched filters will be noisy in a real system.

Ideally the azimuth channels and elevation channels should be similar in shape, and the amplitude difference between them should be as steep as possible while crossing through zero for targets located exactly in the beam steering direction. Ensuring that the matched filters have the same energy content

Fig. 4. Simulated angular peak response of all matched filters at virtual target swept over azimuth, using a 4x1 array with a 256-chip P4 code and $P_n = 0.51$.

by normalizing them to unit energy help with this matter, as well as applying more scrambling weight sets over the length of the pulse for more even average transmit energy distribution over the angles of interest.

An array having the same dimensional spacings but configured as a four-by-one array was used for narrower azimuthal patterns, with a 256-chip P4 sequence code in place of the Barker code for $s(t)$. A set of scrambling weights for each chip within $s(t)$ was applied using $P_n = 0.51$. The matched filters were generated at training angles offset $\pm 10^\circ$ in the azimuth direction. Then in simulation, a single virtual target was swept over -90° to $+90^\circ$ in azimuth. The element waveform sequences were transmitted from the array for each angular position of the virtual test target and the incident waveform at the target was passed through the bank of matched filters. The peak output of the matched filters at the middle index was recorded, and the process was repeated after incrementing the target to the next position. This generates an angular peak response profile for the matched filter channels, the results of which are shown in Fig. 4.

The training angle can be optimized for this array with regard to creating the maximum swing in the difference between positive and negative azimuth channels for localization with better noise immunity. The same four-by-one array and $s(t)$ was used again and one set of scrambling weights per each chip within $s(t)$ was generated. Matched filters were then generated with this set of transmitted signals at test points of $\theta_{az} = [\pm 4^\circ \pm 8^\circ \pm 12^\circ \pm 16^\circ \pm 20^\circ]$. Another virtual target was then swept over azimuth angles while passing the incident signal through the pairs of matched filters formed at these offset angles from the scan direction, creating patterns similar to Fig. 4. The negative azimuth channels were subtracted from the positive azimuth for each pair to create difference patterns, as shown in Fig. 5. Using training angle offsets of half the

Fig. 5. Response of azimuth difference channels ($AZ_{+\theta_n} - AZ_{-\theta_n}$) with training offset angles θ_n listed in the figure, using a 4x1 array with a 256-chip P4 code and $P_n = 0.51$.

Fig. 7. Average elemental S_{11} over the entire nine-by-nine array versus horizontal scan of beam for various values of P_n .

Fig. 6. Statistical plot of active S_{11} for central element of nine-by-nine array versus horizontal scan angle, showing average, min/max, center two quartiles over 3000 sets of scrambling weights for each scan angle, with $P_n = 0.51$.

Fig. 8. Average elemental S_{11} over the entire nine-by-nine array versus diagonal scan of beam for various values of P_n .

angle between the scan direction and the first null of the standard array factor, 16° in this case, creates an approximately linear slope over the widest span. Another benefit of using this as a guideline for the training offset angle causes the nulls in the effective negative and positive azimuth patterns to coincide, thus decreasing the variation in the difference channel further away from the principle scan direction.

III. COUPLING WITHIN DM ARRAY

The maximum scan angle over which a phased array may operate is a typically function of frequency, scan angle, element spacing and structure. The randomized phase weights that directional modulation applies to the elements introduces another factor that must be examined to predict scan

impedance of the array. The scanning impedance is optimized at boresight and the maximum scan angle is typically defined at some angle at which the return loss is too high, often defined at 10 dB. Technically the array system could operate at wider angles but with reduced overall system efficiency as more transmit power is reflected off the array face.

By randomizing the baseband signal applied to each element, the amount and phase of coupling into each element can be varied as a function of time over the length of a signal pulse. For very wide scan angles where aggregate reflected power would be an issue for a standard array, randomization of the applied phase weights can actually lower the average amount of reflected power.

To show the effect on coupling due to randomized phase weights, simulated S-parameter data was collected using HFSS

on a nine-by-nine planar array, which was designed to operate over 3.0-3.6 GHz with element spacings of 45.5 mm. Using this S-parameter data at 3.3 GHz, phase weights were applied in Matlab that scanned the beam to boresight. Randomized scrambling weights were applied with $P_n = 0.707$ to all the elements using a greedy algorithm of four- and three-element solution blocks. This value of P_n reduces the power density of the transmitted signal at the scan angle by 3 dB. The azimuth beam-steering angle was incremented from 0° to 75° and for each increment, 3000 sets of scrambling weights were applied. The statistics for active S_{11} of the central element over the 3000 sets of scrambling weights versus scan angle are shown in Fig. 6. The average active S_{11} at the central element is -10.5 dB with the beam scanned to boresight and stays below -10 dB till $\theta_{az} = 35^\circ$. The active S_{11} stays near the average value over most of the 3000 applications of scrambling weights at each scan angle. The third quartile range limit is approximately 1.5 dB above the average and the first quartile range limit is 6 dB below the average. The maximum recorded active S_{11} was above 0 dB at a few scan angles, for which the elements must have robust front end architectures that can tolerate a transient event with over-unity reflected power.

The average reflected power is a function of the amount of scrambling induced by P_n and also of scan angle, which is shown in Fig. 7 for a horizontal scan and Fig. 8 for a diagonal scan. At very wide scan angles in the horizontal scan of Fig. 7, the average reflected power of the array with scrambling is reduced compared to the traditional array. For instance, at $\theta_{horiz} = 75^\circ$, the average reflected power for the traditional array is -7.0 dBc, while it was -7.9 dBc with $P_n = 0.51$ and averaging the reflected power over 10000 sets of scrambling weights.

While this improvement is slight and overall operation efficiency is not improved due to the reduced signal strength in the main beam direction, the dependency of the scan impedance on the relative element spacing is notable. Wide angle scan impedance can generally be improved by reducing lattice spacing of an array at the expense of some directivity [5]. Application of directional modulation to an array at wide scan angles shows potential for scan impedance improvements while maintaining wide element spacings.

IV. CONCLUSION

A method for constructing directional modulation waveforms for phased array radar applications was expanded upon to show the how the spatial variation of a transmitted signal can be used to indicate location of a target. The simulated and measured responses of matched filters tailored to these waveforms at specific angles were shown, both as a function of training angle and incident angle. Effective average reflected power for large arrays using directional modulation waveforms was also characterized as a function of scan angle and amount of scrambling introduced with directional modulation.

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